

Designing Career Management System Improvement for A Joint Venture Company

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ABSTRACT: In a Joint Venture company with total manpower planning 34 people, career path becomes an issue which impacts the internal condition in the company involving employee satisfaction index and organization need fulfillment. This research observes how employees perceive career management system in the company. The research is done through company document analysis and semi structured interview to the selected samples as the representative of employee. Refer to the result of observation, it is suggested to improve career management system in the joint venture company through implementation of integrated talent management in area development and retention by connecting all talent assessment results to open career opportunity for company self-recruited employee in the level Head of Bureau by unlocking new positions of Head of Bureau to be occupied by company self-recruited employee. Fulfillment of position from assignment from parent company can be made only if there is no candidate for the joint venture internal talent to meet required criteria for that position. This way will contribute to increasing employee retention in the company.

KEYWORDS: Career management system, Joint venture, Talent management

A. INTRODUCTION

People are capital owned by a company to manage stakeholder expectations including business owner, investor, creditor, employees, environment, and society ¹. Human resources management practices should be able to meet employee expectations. Some reasons why employees leave their jobs are ²:

- a. Lack of growth opportunities
- b. Better offering from other companies in remuneration and benefit
- c. Lack of leadership communication transparency
- d. Skills are underutilized
- e. Company instability

Based on the company employee satisfaction survey, the lowest score of satisfaction is low career opportunity in the company even for those who gave continuous contributions. In terms of organization hierarchy, the organization has 3 layers of career paths from operator, head of division, and head of bureau. The top career path is head of bureau. However, these positions are currently prioritized for assignment from the parent company. Therefore, the researcher wants to observe how employees perceive those organizational issues.

Research Question: What is the career management system improvement design for the company?

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

In a joint venture company, commonly there are still multiple parties involved even after an alliance agreement is made. In many cases of joint venture companies, parent companies may have their own interests which lead to some challenges in organization. To overcome challenges in organization, key successful criteria that should be adopted are involving commitment from key persons of assigned employees from parent companies and having a robust willingness to develop joint venture employees ³.

A. Career Management

Career management is the way an organization will fulfill long term needs to improve employees' individual development through human resources planning ⁴. Career planning helps to identify opportunities and needs for employees' careers by developing human resources programs to support that career ⁵. One of the important factors for companies to succeed in the competitive world of the

global economy is attracting and retaining the right talent in the right place ⁶⁾. The word talent is defined as the new employees that are expected to contribute for a high-performance organization ⁷⁾.

B. Integrated Talent Management (ITM)

Integrated Talent Management (ITM) is a group of principles that guides companies to find and support talent in order to reduce talent turnover ⁸⁾. Step by Step Implementation Guide of ITM:

1. **Attracting Talent** through talent planning, recruitment, selection, and orientation.
2. **Developing talent** through performance appraisal, talent mapping, development and learning need analysis, implementation of learning and development, and talent review.
3. **Retaining talent** through career planning, succession planning, and talent engagement ⁹⁾.

C. Building Transparency and Individual Development

Performance appraisal fairness may motivate employees to improve their commitment and job output ¹⁰⁾. If there is an unfair system in the performance evaluation process, employees are unlikely to take the evaluation seriously which then may lead to low motivation in their jobs ¹¹⁾. Fair performance evaluation indicates that:

- a. Employees need to be allowed to take part in the goal-setting process to ensure that they have clear performance objectives every year.
- b. Employees are given a space to state their feelings and ideas about the evaluation shared to them as well to be securely open about their contribution to their supervisor.
- c. Human Resources Management provides enough evidence to rationalize their evaluation and offer employees constructive feedback for their future ¹²⁾.

C. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the concept on how the research is performed. It is started from business issue understanding, continued data collection and analysis to find proper business solution.

Figure 1. Research Concept

A. Data Collection

Organization internal analysis is done to deep dive into situation analysis within the company associated with the career management system and employee engagement. To complete the research with relevant data, the author sets up a data collection method for the entire research like in table 1.

Table 1. Methods of Data Collection

Method	Objectives	Participants
Stage 1 Company internal data analysis	To get picture of organization manpower planning	Head Division of Human Resources and Development
Stage 2 Semi Structured Interview	To get description of employees' point of view regarding their career path	Head of Bureau (2) Head Division (5) Officer (2)

B. Semi Structured Interview

Qualitative approach methodology is selected for this research to make the author concerned in qualitative phenomena related to the motivation and human behaviour in the company since this research is focusing on the development of a career management system for the company¹³⁾. A semi structured interview is going to be applied to collect primary data because this method can help the author to deep dive into the required information in the study¹⁴⁾. There are three main questions used in the Semi-Structured Interview for employees or representatives interview participants.

1. How is your opinion about the company's current career system?
2. How is your opinion about the current career opportunities in the company?
3. What is your target in improving career opportunities in the company?

D. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Company Internal Data Analysis

Manpower planning in the company involves 3 types of employees including:

- a. Assignment from parent company
- b. Company self-recruited employee

There are 3 layers of position structured in the company organization with the highest position is Head of Bureau which are currently 80% occupied by employee's assignment from parent company.

Figure 2. Organization Structure

B. Semi Structured Interview

According to the perspective of employee (9 samples) in perceiving career management system that is obtained through semi structured interview, the result is shown. From response question 1 related to the career management system in the company, it is found that is found that career promotion difficulty becomes dominant key issue.

Table 2. Result of Question 1

Category	Theme	Level of Response
Succession planning	Career promotion difficulty	10
	Career promotion availability	2
Implementation of learning and development	Training and rotation	4
Career planning	Dual system is preferred	1
Performance appraisal	Ineffective performance appraisal	4
Talent Management	Closed talent management	3
Talent engagement	Career relates to motivation and resignation choice	4

In the result of response from 1st question, stagnant career path is the highest component which are explained by the interview samples.

Table 3. Result of Question 2

Category	Theme	Level of Response
Succession planning	Stagnant career path	9
	There is career opportunity	1
	Grade promotion is an option for reward	3
	Career promotion within group	1
Talent engagement	Career relates to motivation and resignation choice	4

In the 3rd question, the employees who want to achieve higher still dominates the response.

Table 4. Result of Question 3

Response	Number of Response
No target	2 (22%)
Follow the condition	1 (11%)
Achieve higher	6 (67%)

E. ANALYSIS AND BUSINESS SOLUTION

From the result of document analysis and semi structured interview results, some improvements are required to make quality increase of career management system in the company aligned with the objective of the company to establish employee reward system through new career path establishment. In this paper, the author suggests the company to implement career management system with Integrated Talent Management concept.

A. Career Management with Integrated Talent Management

The process of talent management is an integrated process which connect potential, achievement, and next steps by considering all aspects of career management system. The process of integrated is illustrated in the following flow diagram. The score (rating) of each requirement shall be determined by the company as the baseline to pass each stage. The evaluation and scoring shall be conducted regularly, the opportunity to compete is equal for all employees in the same level. In this stage, the opportunity will be opened for these 4 positions Head of Bureau.

It is suggested that fulfillment of position from assignment from parent company can be made only if there is no candidate for self-recruited employees (internal talent) to meet required criteria for that position. By implementing this system, it means that the company will be able to integrate talent management system with career path.

Figure 2. Integrated Talent Management

The career management system is objectively designed as the flow in the figure 2 with the detail process description as mentioned in the table 5.

Table 5. Process in Integrated Talent Management

Process	Description
Individual Key Performance Indicator (KPI) Planning	Employee is set target KPI and officially register to the company
Individual Development Project Planning	Employee is set target individual development and officially register to the company
Performance Appraisal	System to appraise employee performance objectively based on their individual achievement in KPI realization
Individual Development Project Evaluation	System to evaluate employee performance to accomplish task of individual development
High Talent Determination	Categorize the high talent employee to be potential candidate in leadership development
Leadership task assignment	Additional leadership assignment tasks for those who are determined as high talent

High Talent Evaluation	Performance evaluation of high talented employee based on their individual performance in all aspects including KPI realization, individual development project accomplishment, and leadership assignment completion
Job & Responsibility enlargement	Direct task that is given by director to an individual to strengthen capability to become leader

B. New Procedure of Performance Appraisal

Employee performance appraisal shall be done objectively in accordance with the employee performance. The company shall determine the score and rating to evaluate employee performance. The score and rating shall be published to employees to ensure that fair competition will be achieved.

Table 6. Result of Question 3

Category	Score	Rating
Lower than target ~ <20%	0-6	E
Lower than target ~ <5%	6.01-7	D
Achieve Target	7.01-8	C
More than target +5%-10%	8.01-9	B
More than target >+10%	9.01-10	A

In the normal operation, performance appraisal is suggested to be conducted at least once in a year by using evidence-based appraisal.

F. CONCLUSION

This research is undertaken to observe how company and employee perceive career management system in the company. Through the steps in stage 1 and stage 2, it is summarized that career path is the key issue for the company in the point of view from employee. Based on the research done to examine career management system in the company, the report concludes that:

1. Improvement of career management system in the company is required to increase employee motivation and improve employee retention since the most voice of the employee is looking for career opportunities from external when they cannot get career opportunity from internal. The improvement is necessary to stabilize company business performance.
2. The improvement is made to meet company strategic initiative in establishing reward system for the employees through establishment of new career path.

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